

IMPORTANCE OF SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY EDUCATION FOR ECUADORIAN FRUIT AND VEGETABLE EXPORTING COMPANIES

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Abstract

A documentary review was carried out on the production and publication of research papers related to studying the variables and importance of social responsibility education for fruit and vegetable exporting companies. The bibliometric analysis proposed in this document was to know the main characteristics of the volume of publications registered in the Scopus database during 2016-2021,

identifying 112 publications. The information provided by the said platform was organized using tables and figures, categorizing the information by Year of Publication, Country of Origin, Area of Knowledge and Type of Publication. Once these characteristics were described, a qualitative analysis was used to refer to the position of different authors on the proposed topic. Among the main findings of this research, it is found that China, with 15 publications, was the country with the highest scientific production registered in the name of authors affiliated with institutions of that country. The area of knowledge that made the greatest contribution to the construction of bibliographic material referring to the study of the importance of education in social responsibility for fruit and vegetable exporting companies was Social Sciences, with 56 published documents, and the type of publication that was most used during the period mentioned above was the journal article, representing 72% of the total scientific production.

Keywords: Social responsibility, export

1. Introduction

Social responsibility is an obligation as human beings and entities to conserve and protect natural resources and life in society voluntarily as a way to contribute to society by striving for its preservation and economic growth without harming the environment. Corporate social responsibility is all actions taken by companies that transparently try to give back to society for actions during business activity that may affect the environment, following ethical principles. Through these actions, corporations fulfill their civic duty and promote the circular economy to reduce the environmental impact, using local products so that the profits stay in the same territory. Social responsibility helps the sustainability in the commercial and operational processes of the company since it seeks to use fewer resources and obtain better profits for companies that export food. This responsibility is much more present since it is used as a development tool for exporting companies to have good practices nationally and internationally, taking into account that this can be affected by pests or other factors in the export of food that can put public health at risk. In the case of Ecuador, which is one of the countries with the highest rates of export of raw materials, it is necessary to apply these actions in order to make the processes more sustainable by having good practices in all commercial and environmental stages that allow generating higher profits without affecting the territory. This is why scientific production reviews encourage its analysis and implementation that allows the carrying out of actions that are intended to meet the objectives of sustainable development given by the UN and encourage the conscious economy of exporting companies.

2. General Objective

To analyze from a bibliometric and bibliographic perspective, the production of research papers on the variable variables Education in Social Responsibility for fruit and vegetable exporting companies during the period 2016-2021.

3. Methodology

A quantitative analysis of the information provided by Scopus under a bibliometric approach on the scientific production related to studying the importance of social responsibility education for fruit and vegetable exporting companies is carried out. Also, from a qualitative perspective, examples of some research papers published in the area of the study mentioned above are analyzed from a bibliographic approach to describe the position of different authors on the proposed topic. The search is performed through the tool provided by Scopus, and the parameters referenced in Figure 1 are established.

3.1 Methodological design

Figure 1. Methodological design

Source: Own elaboration

3.1.1 Phase 1: Data Collection

The data was collected from the Scopus web page search tool, through which 38 publications were identified. For this purpose, search filters were established consisting of:

- ✓ Published papers whose study variables are related to the study of the prevalence and incidence of Human Papillomavirus.
- ✓ No country limitation.
- ✓ Without distinction of area of knowledge.
- ✓ Without distinction of type of publication.

3.1.2 Phase 2: Construction of analysis material

The information identified in the previous phase is organized. The classification will be made through graphs, figures and tables based on data provided by Scopus.

- ✓ Word Co-occurrence.
- ✓ Year of publication
- ✓ Country of origin of the publication.
- ✓ Knowledge area.
- ✓ Type of Publication

3.1.3 Phase 3: Drafting conclusions and final document

After the analysis carried out in the previous phase, the study drafts the conclusions and prepares the final document.

4. Results

4.1 Co-occurrence of words

Figure 2 shows the co-occurrence of keywords within the publications identified in the Scopus database.

Figure 2. Cooccurrence of words

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

As shown in Figure 2, the most used keywords are corporate social responsibility which refers to the activities developed by companies in order to give back to society for the possible effects that commercial activity can generate, also taking into account the needs of the community in which these activities are carried out, these actions are performed from an ethical stance which seeks to promote sustainable growth taking into account both economic and social aspects that allow determining a balance between these two and to have a growth that can be maintained without causing further damage to the environment. In addition, there are keywords such as sustainability, export and sustainable development, which refer to the actions taken by export companies regarding their processes, especially those dedicated to food trade, since they must consider environmental factors that may affect their activity. Hence, their social responsibility is much more implemented since it depends on this that companies can have a balanced and sustainable function

where the basic needs of human beings are supplied without causing further damage to the environment.

4.2 Distribution of scientific production by year of publication.

Figure 3 shows how the scientific production is distributed according to the year of publication, taking into account the period from 2017 to 2021

Figure 3. Distribution of scientific production by year of publication.

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

2021 is the year with the highest number of publications related to the variables under study, presenting 23 papers, including the one titled “Corporate social responsibility strategy, sustainable product attributes and export performance” (Ullah et al., 2021). The current paper is one of the first studies that address the role of corporate social responsibility strategy and its relationship with export performance or whether companies need to adapt CSRS to develop a performance-oriented SPA mix. The empirical analysis uses a panel dataset of 433 U.S. manufacturing firms from 2002 to 2017. The results showed that exporting companies that carried out social responsibility activities performed better, primarily due to the economic incentives provided by the government, as well as the public’s approval since when they learned that the products were made through more sustainable processes, they chose to purchase them instead of other products on the market.

In second place is 2018 with 20 papers titled “Signaling good by doing good: How does environmental corporate social responsibility affect international expansion?” (Xu et al., 2018). This paper analyzes how environmental corporate social responsibility (CSR) facilitates international expansion. Through this analysis, two essential factors are determined: energy conservation and emissions reduction; determined if these affect or help export activities in the perception and optimization of products. It analyzed 425 listed companies from environmentally sensitive industries between 2008 and 2012 in China, finding that a high level of energy

conservation and emission reduction has a significant and indirect effect on export performance, which is mediated by their signaling behavior.

4.3 Distribution of scientific production by country of origin.

Figure 4 shows the distribution of scientific production according to the nationality of the authors.

Figure 4. Distribution of scientific production by country of origin.

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

China is the country with the highest scientific production in the period 2016-2021, presenting 15 papers related to the variables under study within which is the title “Will China’s trade restructuring reduce CO2 emissions embodied in international exports?” (Tang et al., 2017). This paper focuses on analyzing and reducing China’s embodied emissions exports through trade restructuring. In this study, a trade restructuring optimization model combined with input-output analysis and multi-objective programming was established by taking into account the ability of enterprises to take it on. The results suggest that the trade-off cost for China to reduce embodied emissions exports is very high. Thus, re-structuring exports and imports are needed to make these processes more sustainable. Even so, China can still take advantage of several positive factors that have emerged in recent years to improve industrial and energy consumption structures.

At this point, it should be noted that the production of scientific publications, when classified by country of origin, presents a special characteristic: the collaboration between authors with different affiliations to both public and private institutions. These institutions can be from the same country or of different nationalities, so the production of an article co-authored by different authors from different countries of origin allows each country to add up as a unit in the overall publications. This is best explained in Figure 4, which shows collaborative workflow from different countries.

Figure 5. Co-citations between countries.

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

As mentioned above, China is the country with the most significant contribution to research related to the variables under study, having research with countries such as Australia and the United Kingdom to complement research depending on the experience due to the characteristics of each territory. The United States has 11 documents and numerous collaborations with different countries in second place. Within these publications is the one entitled “The export of hazardous industries in 2016” (Castleman, 2016). This document begins an investigation from the premise that With globalization, companies should also be obliged to take responsibility for their suppliers, contractors and separate distributors, and licensees of their technology, taking into account all the affectations that this can treat both the human being and the environment, so in this study, it is proposed that Individual countries must overcome the influence of exporting countries and regulate their industries preventing this from affecting their environment.

4.4 Distribution of scientific production by area of knowledge

Figure 5 shows how the production of scientific publications is distributed according to the area of knowledge through which the different research methodologies are executed.

Figure 6. Distribution of scientific production by area of knowledge.
Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

Social sciences were the area of knowledge with the most significant influence at the time of carrying out research referring to the study of educational programs and their effect on the knowledge and prevention of tuberculosis presenting 56 publications, within which is the title “Analysis of banana and cocoa export commodities in the transformation of the food system, with special reference to certification schemes as drivers of change” (Alho et al., 2021). This document aims to analyze the performance of the food system in terms of health and nutrition, environmental sustainability and income and inclusion. While certification schemes are significant in helping positive transformations of the food system, more innovations are needed to make these food exports much more sustainable, considering that they must have the dignified jobs of primary sector vendors.

4.5 Type of publication

Figure 7 shows how the bibliographic production is distributed according to the author’s chosen publication type.

Figure 7. Type of publication

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

As Figure 7 shows, within the different types of publications, 72% of the total number of documents identified through Phase 1 of the Methodological Design correspond to journal articles, of which is the one entitled “What is driving corporate social and environmental responsibility in China? An assessment of legacy effects, organizational characteristics and transnational pressure” (Chen & Hamilton, 2020). This paper’s main objective is to identify the internal and external, domestic and transnational variables that explain differences in corporate social responsibility performance and performance in specific subfields of Corporate Social Responsibility, such as environmental and community responsibility. The results show that, although they help environmental performance, this does not necessarily mean that it applies to social growth.

5. Conclusions

Thanks to the bibliometric analysis carried out in this article, it is possible to determine that The main characteristics in the volume of scientific production concerning the study of the importance of education in social responsibility for fruit and vegetable exporting companies have a good research flow, so it is established that China, was the country with the highest number of reports through its institutions to Scopus with a total of 15 documents registered during the period 2016-2021. Due to the nature of the study, which seeks to determine the importance of social responsibility education for fruit and vegetable exporting companies, it is established that Social Sciences was the area of knowledge with the most significant influence on the research identified since 56 of the 112 publications related for the present analysis, actively participate with theories framed in that area of knowledge. Similarly, following the nature of the study and the commercial component, the business also played a fundamental role in executing 41 publications. It is worth highlighting that within the analysis presented regarding the position of different authors for the

study of the topic proposed in this research, it can be concluded that social responsibility is all the actions that ethically people and companies take as a way of giving back to society for the damage done to the environment, being more aware of the actions taken in economic and social growth. Social responsibility helps to promote the circular economy, thus giving resources to the territory that helped its creation; for such reason, social responsibility is increasingly adopted by companies in order that their processes are increasingly sustainable, taking into account all the impacts that in the business activity can be given to the environment. In food export companies, these processes are even more important since they must take into account the damage to the soil and the pests that can be caused, so these companies are increasingly opting to use more sustainable processes to obtain higher quality products without compromising natural resources. This is why educational programs are increasingly important in the generation of research projects to determine how social responsibility influences the development of strategies for exporting companies, depending on the commercial activity they develop and thus, be able to determine the actions to follow to make exports a more sustainable and ethical process. However, it is expected that from bibliographic and bibliometric reviews such as the one proposed in this document.

In this sense, it is expected that from bibliographic and bibliometric reviews such as the one proposed in this document, the current situation of the literature on the subject will be taken into account and that educators and the educational and trade community will help in the generation of new knowledge on the subject to have more scientific material to determine the importance of education in social responsibility for fruit and vegetable exporting companies.

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